

USING 3D PRINTING TO ENHANCE STEM TEACHING AND LEARNING

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Abstract STEM stands for Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics, and STEM education refers to an interdisciplinary approach to teaching and learning that integrates these four disciplines to promote critical thinking, problem-solving, and creativity among students. STEM education prepares students with the skills and mindset needed to thrive in the modern workforce and encourages diversity and inclusivity in STEM fields.

3D printing, also known as additive manufacturing, is a rapidly evolving technology that has the potential to greatly enhance STEM teaching and learning. 3D printing allows students to design and create physical objects, providing them with a hands-on learning experience. Students can design and print 3D models of scientific concepts, engineering prototypes, mathematical shapes, and other STEM-related objects. 3D printing can help students visualize abstract concepts that are difficult to understand through traditional teaching methods. 3D printing encourages students to think critically and solve problems creatively. Students need to plan, design, and optimize their 3D models, which requires them to apply critical thinking, problem-solving, and iterative design skills. This can enhance their overall problem-solving abilities, which are essential in STEM fields.

No matter what the curriculum is, 3D printing can help students and teachers work better. 3D printing elevates students from being passive consumers of information on a screen with no thought given to productivity. Unlike conventional classrooms where students are easily bored, they become active and engaged participants through the conception, design, and execution of their projects and interacting with the 3D printer and the teacher.

BOSHLANG'ICH SINIF O'QUVCHILARINI KREATIV FIKRLASHGA O'RGATISHDA EKOLOGIK MASALALARNING ROLI (YANGI AVLOD DARSLIK LARI ASOSIDA)

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Bugungi kunda fan-texnika jadal suratlar bilan rivojlanayotgan bir paytda ekologiyaning buzilishi ko'pchilikni tashvishga solyapti. Tevarak-atrofnı toza tutish, inson hayoti uchun zarur bo'lgan tabiat ne'matlarini avaylab-asrash bugungi kunning dolzarb masalalardan biridir.

Inson tabiat ne'matlaridan foydalanar ekan, ulardan tejab, sof toza holicha kelgusi avlodga yetkazish uchun oqilona yo'l tutishi lozim. Shu sababdan, boshlang'ich sinf ostonasidan o'quvchilarnı tevarak-atrofnı toza tutish, tabiat ne'matlaridan tejamkorlik bilan foydalanish, ekologik muhitni yaxshilash yo'lida o'z hissasini qo'shish tuyg'usini shakllantirish har bir boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchisining muhim vazifalaridan biridir. Matematika darslarida matnli masalarnı yechish jarayonida shu tuyg'uni shakllantirish bo'yicha ancha ishlarnı amalga oshirish mumkin.

Darhaqiqat, ekologik mazmundagi ko'plab hayotiy masalalar matematika darslarida yechilishini nazarda tutsak, bu o'quvchilarda ekologik bilimlarnı shakllantirishga xizmat qiladi. Bu bilan, o'quvchilarnı tabiatni sevishga, unga mehr-muhabbat bilan qarash, tabiat qonuniyatlariga bo'ysunish, uni tafakkur qila olish o'rgatib boriladi.